

IMPLEMENTING AND INCULCATING THE SKILLS IN STUDENT TEACHER

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Abstract:

This research paper explains the implementation and inculcation of skills in student teacher. Good student teachers form the foundation of good schools, and improving teachers' skills is one of the most important investments of time and money that local, state, and national leaders make in education. The wide variety of professional development options available, which methods have the most impact on student learning. If each student teacher recognizes the over-all relationships and significance of the skills. Teacher training program is also important in the education sector same as the teacher training institution. The need for training in education particularly for student teachers is important to improve the quality of education.

Keywords: Implementing, Inculcating, Skills, Student teacher, teaching-learning .

Introduction:

A quality student teacher comes from a quality education process. A carefully designed and well planned education system is critical to developing such human capital. Thus, institutions of teacher education play a very important role to produce a human capital that is highly knowledgeable and skillful to meet the demand and expectations of many people. The teaching and learning processes in institutions of teacher education should be capable to provide such knowledge and skills to perspective

teachers. The curriculum process of the teacher education should be capable of providing some knowledge and skills for teachers in conceptual and soft skills apart from hard skill. Infusing the soft skills in the curriculum of teacher education is the need of the profession for it to be successful. The teacher educators providing some knowledge and skills for student teacher in conceptual and soft skills apart from hard skill. Infusing the soft skills in the curriculum of teacher education is the need of the profession for it to be successful. Soft skills are personal attributes that enhance an individual's interactions, job performance and career prospects and hard skills which tend to be specific to a certain type of task or activity. We could say that soft skills refer to personality traits, social gracefulness, fluency in language, personal habits, friendliness and optimism that mark to varying degrees. Soft skills complement hard skills which are the technical requirements of a profession. It can also be an important part of the organization especially if the organization is dealing with people face to face. The reorientation of education which is one trust of education for sustainability also relates the importance of these so-called soft skills. Vast research and expert opinions have been sought in the effort to determine the specific soft skills to be implemented and used in teacher education programme. Based on the research findings obtained, seven soft skills have been identified and chosen to be implemented in all institutions of teacher education.

The foremen had grown away from their old practices, and strong foreman leadership, the traditional job-shop operations proved costly and inefficient. In this instance, when the new production controls and formalized institution. The study found that teachers were more likely to change their instructional practices and gain greater subject knowledge and improved teaching skills when their professional development linked directly to their daily experiences and aligned with standards and assessments.

Objective:

1. To study the Implementation of Skills in Student Teacher .
2. To Inculcate the skill in Student Teacher.
3. To suggest the various skills for student teacher.
4. To Implementing and Inculcating the Skills in Student Teacher.

Sample of the study : The survey encompassed the views of both student teacher admitted during the year 2016-2017. Of the 35 registered students, only 35 made it into the sample drawn proportionally through the stratified random sampling.

Tools of the Study:-The present study was a survey and as such data for this study were solicited through the questionnaires included structured questions., a survey questionnaire used for the purpose of this study, which contained both open and closed

ended questions.

Data Collection: The standard of student teachers almost similar. The total 35 student teacher selected randomly, out of these 35 was selected for treatment. The investigators personally contacted all the trainee students who were studying in B.Ed. In the year 2016-2017 and distributed the questionnaire to them after a polite request.

Data Analysis:-In the research paper the impact of effective administration into three basic skills is useful primarily for purposes of analysis. In practice, these skills are so closely interrelated that it is difficult to determine where one ends and another begins. Also, under different playing conditions the relative importance of these elements varies. Similarly, although all three are of importance at every level of administration, the technical, human, and conceptual skills of the administrator vary in relative importance at different levels of responsibility. Data collection and analysis is essential to understand and develop appropriate responses to design, implement and evaluate research study responses and programmatic interventions in research paper.

Table No.1
Implementing and Inculcating the Skills in Student Teacher

Teacher students	X= x-M ₁	Y= y-M ₂	XY	X ²	Y ²
Average	2.18	1.12	3.35	6.2	1.85
Mean	3.28	1.35	7.2	15.8	2.96

Graph No.1
Implementing and Inculcating the Skills in Student Teacher

Conclusion:-

The purpose of this paper has been to show that Implementing and Inculcating the Skills in Student Teacher This three-skill approach emphasizes that good administrators are not necessarily born; they may be developed. The changing goals for learning, coupled with shifts in curriculum emphasis and a deeper understanding of teacher learning and student thinking, have led to new findings about the impact of teacher professional development and how best to sharpen teachers' skills and knowledge. Professional development should improve teachers' knowledge of the subject matter that they are teaching, and it should enhance their understanding of student thinking in that subject matter. Aligning substantive training with the curriculum and teachers' actual work experiences also is vital. The time teachers spend in professional development makes a difference as well, but only when the activities focus on high-quality subject-matter content. Extended opportunities to better understand student learning, curriculum materials and instruction, and subject-matter content can boost the performance of both teachers and students.

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